

A Sensation based Model of Product elicited Emotions

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Abstract

Recent years have seen ‘*designing for emotions*’ (DFe) as a new emerging field in product design. Such a design approach can provide companies with a much desired competitive edge if adopted successfully. Research work is today attempting to overcome the intricacies encountered with DFe by investigating different aspects of the user-product interaction experience such as the role of human senses. This research paper highlights the work undertaken in this direction at the University of Malta via a research project entitled *DemoHS* with a focus on the development of a new model of product-emotions based on the sensations generated during product interaction.

Keywords: DFX, Senses, User-product interaction, Sensagram

1.0 Introduction

The significance of the design process in determining the success or failure of a product in the market place is becoming increasingly more articulated and consequently new techniques and tools to support design more effectively are being implemented (Duffy 1993). However such design support tools very often focus on product functionality and this is resulting in products not being designed for their '*x-abilities*' such as *manufactur-ability*, *assimil-ability*, *service-ability*, etc (Duffy 1993, Borg 2000). Good product functionality does not necessarily lead to product *purchase*, *use* or *acceptance* by customers (McDonagh 2003). We are in fact at a point in time where companies can no longer compete simply on technology, mainly because many companies are facing competitors that are equal in technical expertise (Formosa 2005). Due to today's tendencies in product development it is becoming more likely that many future products will become functionally equivalent and therefore hard to distinguish between for the customer (Schutte 2005). This will result in customers' choice of products being based on highly selective criteria, which go beyond the functional and are referred to as *supra-functional*. Such criteria are linked to users' *cultural*, *social*, *tribal*, *spiritual*, *emotional* and *inspirational* needs (Watson 2004), with the emotional domain emerging as one of the most vital. Most human interaction with the material world involves emotions including user-product interaction, and products are nowadays being increasingly designed to attempt to address this emotional experience. Addressing the emotional needs of customers is an area that is being attributed increasing importance in the design world, and designing for product-emotions is by now considered as a new member of the *design for X* (DFX) family. *Pleasure*, *desire*, *surprise*, *irritation*, *disgust*, etc. are all emotions that we experience when interacting with products. Products also manage to elicit emotions inside use prior to their purchase such as the *desire* for a pair of shoes we see in a shop window or else the *envy* for our neighbour's brand new sports car (Fenech 2006). It is no longer sufficient for a product to function properly, be usable and efficient or have aesthetic appeal, but it also has to provide positive emotional responses (Desmet 2002). Such responses have large influences on purchase decisions (Holbrook 1985) since they can incite customers to pick a particular model from whole rows of other similar products (Desmet 2002).

This research paper discloses the results being achieved in the field of emotion-driven product design with a focus on the design knowledge being developed via an ongoing research project entitled *DemoHS*. Section 1 thus introduced the concept of product-emotions. The major

intricacies encountered in emotion-driven design as well as the mechanisms involved in user-product interaction are then reviewed in sections 2 and 3 respectively. The model developed under *DemoHS*, the theory leading to its development and the results collected during its testing are then presented and analysed in sections 4-7. Finally some important conclusions and points of future work are made in section 8.

2.0 Problem Background

Measuring user satisfaction and emotion is difficult or at least, extremely subjective (Cardoso 2005), but to actually *design* for satisfaction and emotion is considered (by some) even more unattainable. The major intricacies encountered in emotion driven design are attributed to the fact that product-emotions are *idiosyncratic*. This is because different people relate to different products in their own personal way, depending upon the product's characteristics and their own (McDonagh 2003). Some people might find a particular product to evoke positive emotions, while other people find the same product to evoke negative emotions. This implies that designing a product to suit many individuals, where each individual is unique is indeed a challenging task (Janhager 2005). Past *design for emotion* (DFe) attempts have been focussed on a redesign approach, based on the emotional evaluation of already existing products with potential users. However, such a design strategy, although being deemed as successful, cannot be utilised for the design of new products. This means that the DFe of new products brings forward new problems that are not encountered when adopting a redesign strategy, since in *new product development*, users with experience of the product to be developed do not exist (Janhager 2005).

Although significant work has been conducted in the identification of the mechanisms involved in the emotive part of product interaction, a general lack of knowledge of the product-emotion elicitation process persists. The actual *interface* between users and products and how this gives rise to emotions has been somewhat neglected. This therefore exposes a relevant *research gap* since there is still need to investigate the mechanisms involved during user-product interaction that successively give rise to the elicitation of product-emotions. For this purpose, a much needed, clearly defined, DFe framework for product designers is still lacking. Adequate DFe support will enable designers to overcome the intricacies encountered and cater for the *supra-functional* aspect of user-product emotional interaction as a means of improving the market competitiveness of their products.

In this respect an area of relevance is human senses and the role that these occupy in our interaction with products. During our interaction with the material world senses serve as a medium that give rise to perceived sensations prior to appraisal with our *personal* concerns. Therefore investigating the role that senses occupy in the emotional user-product experience can potentially unearth new knowledge that could provide the basis for the development of the much needed design for product-emotion framework.

3.0 The *DemoHS* Research Project

A currently ongoing research project being conducted at the *Concurrent Engineering Research Unit (CERU), University of Malta* and entitled “*Research into Developing ‘Design for Emotion’ Support via Human Sensations – DemoHS*”, is attempting to overcome the mentioned problems. *DemoHS* is aimed at developing a framework in the form of guidelines and/or methodology to product designers in emotion-driven design by clearly investigating the role that senses occupy in user-product interaction.

3.1 Understanding Senses, Sensations and Perceptions

The perception of a product which acts as a stimulus of emotions is within itself a multi-stage process in which senses occupy a key role. As indicated in this conference’s call text; “*the emotional impact of a product is determined by how we see, hear, taste and feel it*”, i.e. by our sensations upon interacting with it. So senses occupy a major role in our interaction with products. They allow us to experience products on different levels since it is through our five senses (*sight, touch, hearing, taste and smell*) that we interact with a product. We *feel* its texture, we *see* its form-features, we *smell* its scent, etc. All that we learn about, and do with the product involves our five senses. In product interaction senses can be subdivided in two distinct categories; the *distance* and the *proximity* senses. Distance senses refers to those senses that can be perceived from a distance such as *hearing, sight and smell*, while proximity senses are those senses that can only be perceived through physical interaction with the artefact, such as *taste and touch* (Ludden 2004). This thus suggests that ‘*the role of distance senses is fundamental for the success of a product*’ since this group of senses is likely to be employed all throughout the product interaction process.

Figure 1, Perception of a product stimulus, adopted from Fenech 2006

The use of senses in product interaction gives rise to two further stages that precede the elicitation of the product-emotions, and are known as *sensations* and *perceptions*. Sensation refers to the process of detecting a stimulus in the environment/surroundings (Figure 1). This is accomplished via *sensory organs* such as the eyes, ears, nose, skin, tongue, etc., that absorb energy from a physical stimulus in the environment and convert these energies into signals that are sent to the brain (Levine 1991). On the other hand, perception involves the organisation of these signals that are then translated into something meaningful through comparison with experience and/or knowledge in the brain.

This identifies the role of senses in the elicitation of product-emotions as being the source for the generation of user sensations from the stimulus (product) in the environment. The sensations are then developed in perceptions upon comparison with knowledge in the brain. The perceived stimulus subsequently takes part in the appraisal process that ends in the product-emotions generated. The above therefore reveals senses as the major source giving rise to product-emotions since it is through senses that all the subsequent stages leading to the final emotions are generated. This thus brings forward the hypothesis onto which *DemoHS* is structured, i.e. that a multi-sensory product appeal can improve the user-product interaction experience since the modalities for interaction with products are greater. A product that successfully appeals to all five of the human senses is expected to interact on a larger scale with the user than one that appeals to maybe only two senses.

3.0 The *DemoHS* Model of Product-Emotions

The material discussed in section 4 has been used to develop a new model of product-emotions in *DemoHS* (Figure 2). This model is aimed at building on past design knowledge while looking at a wider picture of the product-emotion elicitation process. The model structure developed up till now provides a basis for its future development, primarily through a detailed understanding of the product-emotion elicitation process as highlighted by its 8 phases. The *DemoHS* model of product-emotions is in fact based on the theory that upon interaction of the *user* (1) (having his/her own personal *concerns* (2)) with the *product* (3) via senses, *sensations* (4) are generated (Fenech 2006). These result in the *perception* of the *stimulus* (5) after comparison with knowledge/experience in the user's brain. It is the *appraisal* (6) of the perceived stimulus with the user's goals, standards and attitudes that gives rise to the final elicited *emotion* (7). The *novelty* and *strength* of the model is that the linkage between the product and the remainder of the emotion elicitation process (starting from perception of the stimulus by the user, up to the final emotion), is provided through the user's senses. This is missing in other product-emotion models and thus brings forward the premise that through designing for simulating the senses in a specific way, product designers can actually address and overcome the hurdles encountered in emotion driven design (Fenech 2006). The model is therefore based on the hypothesis that '*emotional responses to products are largely influenced by the degree to which the product appeals to our senses*'. Clearly, all this is based on theory, but if proved correct through testing and evaluation, could provide the basis for the development of the much desired '*design for emotion*' support.

Figure 2, The *DemoHS* model of product-emotions

5.0 Testing of the *DemoHS* Model of Product-Emotions

5.1 Preliminary Testing

Preliminary testing of the *DemoHS* model (presented in Fenech 2006) was aimed at the identification of the various phases portrayed in the model and no attempt at proving the linkage between these phases was made. A series of products were presented in turn to a number of participants who were asked to interact with (and use) the products for a short period of time, after which interview sessions were held. The verbal reporting approach used enabled the compilation of a set of results that show:

1. The different emotions elicited for each product;
2. The sense modalities used in the perception of product features acting as stimuli;
3. The user concern giving rise to the emotion appraisal process.

The results obtained hence prove that the interaction experience with a product is indeed based on the use of *different* sense modalities for the perception of various product features that serve as a stimulus to emotions.

5.2 Further in-depth Testing

Further in-depth testing of the *DemoHS* model was however required in order to promote the scientific value of the research work being conducted and justify the hypothesis that a higher

sensory product appeal leads to a higher intensity emotional experience. In particular, quantification of the results obtained (i.e. the degree of senses used and the intensity of emotions generated) was essential in order to support the interim conclusions made in the preliminary testing phase.

5.2.1 Identification and Quantification of the Use of Senses in Product Interaction

The number of senses as well as the degree to which a product appeals to the five senses can be identified and quantified by making use of a *sensagram* (Lindstrom 2005), see Figure 3. This is a pentagram where each corner is assigned to a different sense modality with a scale that varies from a minimum rating of 1 to a maximum of 5. The higher the rating the more does the product appeal to the sense modality in question.

Figure 3, A *sensagram* shows the sensory appeal a product, modified from Lindstrom 2005

The sensagram provides a way in which a product's sensory performance can be quantified, and as portrayed in Figure 5 the larger the area covered by the sensagram, the greater are the product's connections to senses. Based on the work conducted under *DemoHS* the sensagram model has been modified from that developed by Lindstrom in order to better suit the purposes of the research being conducted. *Proximity* and *distance* sense modalities have been grouped in adjacent vertices of the pentagram. The shape of the resulting sensagram can hence quickly indicate if a product has strong connections to a particular sense category.

Sensagram scores can therefore be computed to enable the comparison between different values of *total*, *proximity* and *distance* sensory appeal for different products.

5.2.2 Identification and Quantification of Product-Emotions

In a similar manner the emotions generated during product interaction can be identified and measured. This can be done by making use of a non-verbal self report method that is based on the Russell's circumplex of emotional affect (Russell 1980), see Figure 4a.

This is an organised two-dimensional representation in circular structure, or a '*circumplex*' of product elicited emotions. Developed by Russell, the circumplex plots different emotions along two bipolar axes where the *pleasantness* dimension runs from *pleasure* to *displeasure* and the *arousal* dimension runs from *arousal* to *sleepiness*.

Figure 4, a) Russell's circumplex model of affect, reproduced from Russell 1980, and b) some of the emocards in the circumplex model, reproduced from Desmet 2001

Since it is very difficult for users to express their emotions in vocabulary, the non-verbal self report system '*Emocards*' (Figure 4b) was developed by Desmet et al. (Desmet 2001) that makes use of a set of facial characters. Each character corresponds to a particular emotional state and instead of relying on the use of words participants report their emotions using this expressive cartoon character. Corresponding scores (from 1-5) must once again be indicated in order to quantify the intensity of the emotions generated.

5.2.3 Testing Procedure

The detailed testing stage was conducted over two sessions – an *interaction* and a *self-report* session. In the first session, 6 different products (Figure 5) were physically presented in turn to 15 participants who were asked to interact (and use) the products for a short period of time.

Figure 5, The six products used during the in-depth testing phase

Following product interaction, an interview session with each participant was held. The interviews were based on a self-report approach for the determination of:

- a) The degree of use of senses during product interaction;
- b) The intensity of the emotions generated following product interaction.

The participants were therefore asked to indicate scores (from 1-5) for each sense modality and corresponding emotions generated in connection to the products used during testing. Although participants were asked to indicate one particular *emocard* following each product interaction session, no attempts during testing were made to investigate the type of emotions generated in relation to the sensory appeal of the same products. Under investigation was only the intensity of the elicited emotions.

6.0 Results

The sensory score results obtained were used for the computation of sensagrams for each product (see figure 7). The sensagrams show how the six products connect to senses with the resulting shapes quickly giving an idea of the products' appeal to the *distance* and *proximity*

sense categories. It can be observed that all products exhibit strong connections to touch and sight, thus confirming these two senses as the predominant senses in product interaction.

Figure 6, The computed sensagrams for the six products used in testing

The results (as portrayed in figure 8) show that there is indeed a relation between the sensory level of appeal and the intensity of emotions generated for the six products under test. A clear trend in the data obtained is evident since it can be observed that the higher the sensagram scores, the higher is the intensity of the generated emotions. Products 4 and 6 registered the highest *total sensory* scores (4.28 and 4.31 respectively) and the corresponding highest *emotion intensity* scores (3.29 and 3.71 respectively). This is justified by the fact that these two products have strong connections to both *smell* and *hearing* (besides *sight* and *touch* that are appealed to by most products). All the remaining products have considerably low sensagram scores (< 4) and corresponding low emotion intensity scores (< 3).

Figure 7, Graph of *product sensagram* and *emotion intensity* scores

The data trends observed are also confirmed by the statistical analysis tests conducted on the data obtained. The *Pearson Chi-Squares* (χ^2) test of independence was conducted in order to test for any associations between the two categorical variables under investigation. It was first hypothesised that there is no association between the *sensagram value* and the *emotion intensity* for the different products. The results obtained showed that the p-value was significantly low (i.e. $p < 0.001$) and less than the level of significance (i.e. $p = 0.005$), hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This thus confirms the hypothesis that for the six products tested, those with a higher sensory appeal have greater connections to emotions.

7.0 Conclusions and Future Directions

Designing for emotions is a highly interesting field but without appropriate underlying specific theories and methodologies is difficult to implement. The ongoing research work reviewed in this paper provides a basis for the development of such DFe theories and methodologies, and for overcoming the intricacies encountered when adopting such a design approach. Indeed this can be achieved by a corresponding design approach that starts out by evaluating the signals emitted by a range of different products, and the sensations perceived by all the sensory systems during interaction. In this way the designer can then unearth a combination of ways to stimulate the product user. This hence provides a foundation for the determination of the characteristics that make one product more enjoyable than another, and hence the development of the much needed DFe support. Although the results obtained for the six products under investigation are satisfying, further testing and development in *DemoHS* is required in order to obtain further generic results. Further work will attempt to identify the nature of the relationships that have been proved to exist between the use of senses during interaction and the elicited product-emotions. Any difference in the role between distance and proximity senses is another area that will be investigated. Future work is also needed in attempting to improve the scientific value of the model, for example by considering the role of the environment/surroundings on the product-emotion elicitation process. Only then can the knowledge developed, together with the results and indications obtained be exploited for the development of the required DFe support. Nonetheless, the research work developed together with the evaluation results presented in this paper, indicate that the proposed model delivers a relevant contribution to the development required for adopting a DFe approach.

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